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Caste Dynamics and the Phenomenon of Outcasting: An Exploratory Study of Jatkat in Bihar

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Abstract

This study explores the complex interplay between caste and culture in Bihar, focusing on the phenomenon of outcasting, locally referred to as "Jatkat." The research investigates how caste dynamics influence social interactions, norms, and values within different castes, particularly in inter-caste and inter-religious marriages. The study examines the consequences of outcasting, including the challenges faced by individuals and families who lose their caste membership. It also considers the broader implications of these dynamics on social institutions such as family, religion, economy, and education. Through intergenerational surveys and data analysis from the Patna district, the research provides insights into the sociological perspectives of outcasting and its impact on both rural and urban settings. The findings highlight the persistent influence of caste in Indian society, despite the growing prevalence of out-of-caste marriages, and underscore the need for further research on the evolving nature of caste and social stratification in modern India.

Keywords: Caste dynamics; Casting and Casting Out; Jatkat.

Introduction:

Caste is not just a culture, however; it is a social system involved with various caste dynamics which usually differ from one caste to another. The manner a caste regulates its social objectives, solidarity, norms, values, and philosophy is usually studied under the academic discipline culture of a particular social group or caste. The caste dynamics usually regulate the members of a particular social group or caste that would interact and transact with other members of the caste and with other social groups or castes. The caste dynamics have been deeply involved with religious, economic, political, and geographical considerations.

Out of caste people also commonly referred to as *Jatkat* resulted because of such people losing the membership of a particular caste because of certain reasons mainly inter caste or interreligious marriages. There are several other reasons also. Sometimes, it becomes difficult to determine the caste of children taking birth because of inter-caste or inter-religious marriages. The number of such marriages is increasing day by day which is giving birth to new social problems. Such people usually adopt new norms, values, philosophy, and means of solidarity. On one side so-called progressive people denouncing the caste system and contrary to that now political parties and governments are engaged and demanding a caste-based census which would further give a boost and strength to the caste system.

This particular study would try to explore the culture of the outcasted people which are commonly referred to as *Jatkat* i.e. out of caste in Bihar. Therefore, this research would expedite the explanatory possibilities of caste as a culture, and social systems institutions. The manner social and cultural norms, values, order, and control are regulated. The manner caste system is regulated through social institutions such as family, state, economy, education, and religion.

Once any individual loses the membership of his or her caste it becomes almost impossible for him or her to make a reentry in the caste system. Caste is deeply rooted in our society and culture which has thousands of years of history. Progressive type of people usually try to downplay the caste system, however, still, there are caste-based reservations in India that are constitutionally valid. Moreover, caste surveys are conducted in some states and there were political demands to conduct such surveys all over the country.

Casting and *Casting Out* have been two major phenomena that are required to be studied under the caste dynamics. Both are opposite, however, have a certain major influence on daily-to-daily social transactions.

Casting out results in a member of a society losing membership in what has been referred to as a *Jatkat* in local vernaculars. It also sometimes symbolizes falling in status, prestige, and social exclusion. Casting may symbolize common rules, practices, territory, endogamy, and solidarity. The main reason for a *casting out* is the defiance of rules by any member of the society or family especially in inter-caste and inter-religious marriages. However, this is not the sole reason. The majority castes in Bihar followed certain customary rules, and any deviance was ascertained by the collective decision of the majority. There are methods of creating a majority and imposing punishments. In some cases, the punishment could be extremely harsh and may put life and property in danger. In Bihar, caste as a culture and social system has acquired certain unusual dimensions which attracted scholars, sociologists, and anthropologists. Nowadays genetic scientists are also deeply involved in studying genome sequences of certain castes. In general, a caste system is marked by solidarity, endogamy, and hierarchy, sharing a common profession, territory, and culture. Caste certainly has certain ethnic and biological ingredients also. Caste does matter a lot in the case of marriage, political, economic, religious, and cultural practices.

Out-of-caste marriages resulted due to people of different castes traditionally living aloof and apart being allowed to come closer and interact mutually due to democratization, and urbanization, which largely affected the manner social institutions functioned in a particular society.

Out-of-caste marriages are present as an undercurrent or the dynamics within all social groups or castes that are more visible or reported in urban areas. However, in rural areas, the rigid patriarchy, caste dynamics, and institutions still do not sanction out-of-caste or religious marriages. Therefore, in rural areas casting out is very strong whereby married couples, their children, and even their larger family members lose their caste identity and are labelled as out castes or *jatkat*.

Because of number of marriages increasing day by day the number of out-of-caste people is also increasing with almost the same proportion. In many cases, even family members also oppose out-of-caste or religious marriages and their relationship ceases to exist. Still, such families get out cast.

There are caste organizations which regulate the caste system. They have a very strong social media presence and even used to post the story of any out-of-caste or religious marriages taking place in their community. They intimidated other members of the community to not have any relationship with such persons.

The membership of any caste is determined by birth which would never change. Since it is by birth, caste is a closed society. There is no other option to become a member of a particular caste.

Statement of problem:

Out-casted people more precisely their children disclosing names of their castes. They do even not select either the caste of mother or father.

It could be a distinct social problem in India that could have different perspectives in different castes and rural and urban areas. In rural areas, outcastes resulted due to not obeying certain rules of the caste and disobeying the authority to enforce rules. However, in urban areas, castes mainly resulted due to out-of-caste and religious marriages that were not sanctioned by the larger society. It could also be said that since out of caste, marriages were most often harshly dealt with in rural areas, despite certain legal provisions therefore such practices were very rare in villages. However, in rural areas, certain casual or regular deviant behavior also promoted outcasting. Outcastes could refer to a social group detached, put into exile, seized to be a member of any particular social group, and excluded. Outcastes thoroughly existed within a particular social group, association, or organization and were regulated through different primary and secondary social institutions. There have been varied reasons for the origin of outcastes in India since the ancient period. Outcastes largely resulted due to marital and sexual relationships between persons of different social strata.

Under the premises of a rigid caste system, castes existed in numbers, especially in urban areas. The process of urbanization has brought several castes close to each other in urban settings and due to vicinity, love, dowry, and other factors out of caste marriages took place. Castes are identified easily in rural settings, intermingled, and not easily identified in urban settings.

Certain features of caste systems such as ethnicity, heredity, hierarchy, and endogamy could be due to outcasting. Outcasting resulted mainly due to caste or out-of-religious marriages however there could be several other factors also such as deviant behavior, diseases, bigamy, polygamy, instinctual behavior, foreign visits-immigration, criminal acts, non-respect of the institutions, failed anticipated response and action, homosexuality, incest, family feud, etc. Outcastes could be seen as a result of to imposition of norms and values by different social institutions especially the majority of a particular community deciding unfavorably.

Sociologically, an outcast could be a person who is made to suffer from social stigma or untouchability, total or partial rejection from home or society, or who may be as socially excluded, exiled, or ignored. Caste and outcast are an ancient tradition in India as most of the castes originated due to Outcaste over the centuries. Sometimes several outcast social groups formed a caste of their own and this provided them the stability of status and power, and they also selected roles in the larger society.

Objectives:

This study aimed to expedite various explanatory sociological perspectives of outcasting. Outcastes have different perspectives, modalities, and orientations in urban and rural contexts. Therefore, this study analyzed the extent and pattern of outcasting in India to understand the determinants of outcasting as well as the functioning of different social institutions and their impacts on the caste system in rural and urban settings. The outcastes could be a social problem that requires attention by sociologists in modern contexts for studying outcastes, their social mobility, and stratification. In addition, it was also needed to study the relationships of outcastes with various social groups, associations, and institutions. It was expected that the study would significantly contribute to the existing sources on caste, outcastes, social institutions, and control dynamics.

Statement of the problem

Caste dynamics have been more studied in terms of politics, however, it still needs to be studied amidst certain sociological and economic premises. The manner a particular caste organizes its social interactions both within and outside the caste has not been properly studied. Even a selection of a profession or an economic activity required quantification. The question remains answers to why people preferred to vote and marry within the caste and what factors promoted a person to defy caste rules.

There is a lack of information about the reasons people chose to marry their respective castes. Even the various features of casting and casting out have not been reported properly because each caste has different systems to regulate its caste affairs.

Bihar is synonymous with caste politics and it is very much part of daily-to-daily social transactions. People used to identify and recognize an individual by caste or tend to do so.

In general, several sociologists have outlined outcastes as untouchables or a social group fallen in status. In India, there has been a problem of ancient Hindu apartheid that are not so presented. Outcastes in modern days could not way termed as those ethnic, racial, and cultural apartheid nevertheless the problem existed in the modern society in India among both rural and urban areas. The caste system is under tremendous stress due to casting out and not allowing the entry of children in any particular caste because born out of inter-caste marriages. The situation could emerge as a major social problem and demand assessment, measurement, and dedicated studies. It could cause tremendous social unrest and conflicts in the future. Caste and outcastes always remained two major social groups in the entire course of Indian history.

Several misconceptions existed even among literate people about caste, class, Varna, and the gotra system in India because of the different versions available difficult to pick anyone. One of the problems associated with out of caste marriages has been associated with children that made to face social stigma without having any choice. Although the term out caste could not be synonymous with untouchables or *Achut* however; it could be locally referred to as *Jatkat* which used to be a matter of great abuse or discrimination.

Out castes existed in India since the ancient period, however, not been studied according to modern sociological methods and customs. There is a tremendous data gap about the sociology and physiology of the outcastes in India. Out of caste, marriages are often crippled with unique challenges that are associated with maintaining barriers. Experts claim that it is a natural tendency of people to create barriers in their minds and around them. The problem is about security, preservation, and protection of the society. Society is nurtured in such a way to enclose humanity within particular boundaries, limits, and observations, right from birth to the entire course of socialization. Therefore, certain things are intrinsic to this problem and that becoming difficult to deal with.

Out-of-caste marriages face big hurdles in the light of their decision to defy all and maybe the basic norms of society. Out-of-caste marriage is usually subjected to face problems in adapting to a new environment, culture, and rituals. In many societies out of caste, marriages are considered a serious deviance and cost life. The discord created between the two families and the couple could take any adverse course at any time.

It is not so that outcasting only existed within a caste system or resulted due to inter-caste marriages, however, it also existed within different other social groups such as class, ethnicity, race, languages, religion, professions,

nationality, race, and regional. There has been a tremendous struggle between patriarchy, the caste system, social institutions, and individuals of different social groups that require study.

There has been a lack of data, on the manner caste dynamics work in Bihar. In addition, there was no information or literature in Bihar regarding the two sociological phenomena of castes and out-of-castes. Both are significant ingredients of the caste dynamics.

Overview of literature:

J. Sekhon describes in her book about the modern state shaping society along with other issues such as the history of the country, its religions, its social stratification system, its economic status and role in the global economy, gender relations, its political institutes, and social changes that have taken place in India (Sekhon, 2000). She further explained how religion, economics, and politics play a role in shaping the stratification system of India.

L. Dumont tried to define *caste* and explain the necessity and undeniable need to have the caste system in Hinduism in India. He also explains the caste system and the role it plays in the division of labor in Indian society (Dumont, 1970).

A. Ostor, L. Fruzzetti, and S. Barnett in their book highlighted the plights of the “Untouchable” (Ostor, 1982).

Andre Béteille in his book provided details on the physical structure of the village in India and highlighted the economic organization of the caste system and social class. He also provided an overview on the distributions of power within the caste system (Béteille, 1965).

G. S. Ghurye in his book *Caste and Race in India*, described politics playing a huge role in the shaping of caste (Ghurye, 1969).

J.H Hutton in his book *Caste in India: Its Nature, Function, and Origins*. Detailed caste structure, its sanctions, and endogamous characters.

R.K Lahiri, in his book *Caste System in Hinduism*, provided an account of various characteristics and criteria of different castes and their important roles in society. He also described classifications of caste in terms of occupation, marriage, and discrimination. The book further describes the origins of the caste system (Lahiri, 2005). In ancient texts, we could find terms such as *Varnashankars*, *Chandals*, and *Malecchs*, and in modern sociology, they could be referred to as outcastes.

There were several other literature and studies about inter-caste or inter-religious marriages in India, however, most of them were silent over the problems of casting out. *C.T. Kannan* studied 149 inter-caste marriages in the city of Bombay and found that inter-caste marriage is steadily increasing (Kannan, 1963). Another study on inter-caste marriage by *Reddy* showed that the scheduled caste exhibited the highest tendency for inter-caste marriages than the other castes (Reddy, 1984). He also found that urban residence could be a reason for inter-caste marriages. *K.M Kapadia*, in a study of inter-caste marriages in India, interviewed 513 university graduates and found that 51 percent of parents expressed their willingness to cheer children marrying outside their caste and only one-third were against this departure from custom (Kapadia, 1958). *K. Saroja* found that at a higher level of study, especially at the postgraduate level students were moderately in favor of inter-caste marriage (Saroja, 1999). *N. Prasad* in his study found that urbanization and industrialization had a certain effect on breaking down the barriers of caste (Prasad, 1957). Almost similar viewpoints were expressed by *Banerjee* after a study of a social group in Kolkata (Banerjee, 1978).

Research questions of hypothesis

1. What are the common causes, consequences, and problems of out-of-caste marriages?
2. What are the characteristics of outcaste marriages in different settings such as rural-urban, rich-poor, high caste-low caste, and class divide?
3. What are the generational and intergenerational features of out-of-caste marriages and outcasting?

Research Methodology

An intergenerational survey of out-of-caste marriages in the urban Patna district was conducted from March 2014 to July 2014. It's expected that in India almost 6.14 percent of total marriages were performed out of caste (Das, 2009). Data on caste marriages for the last 10 years was obtained from the district registrar for marriages at Patna. Such data provided name, address, caste, and religion. A generational and an intergenerational survey

of selected populations was conducted taking care of the fact that all classes of people including socially and economically get included appropriately.

Information about the caste and religion of the husband and wife was also collected. The information collected on caste grouped into four categories, namely Scheduled Tribe (ST), Scheduled Caste (SC), Other Backward Classes (OBC), and Upper castes.

Both bivariate and multivariate analyses were used for the analysis. To examine effects of socio-economic factors on out-casting and out-castes, a logistic regression analysis was carried out in which the dependent variable was out-castes, and independent variables included:- caste, caste category, age, residence, income level before and after marriage, income of families before and after marriage, education, religion, working status, household structure, standard of living and mass media exposure, number of children, years of marriage, separation-desertion or divorce.

Findings

While studying the data of registered marriages in Patna, the foremost observation was that most of the marriages registered with the registrar of marriages at Patna were either performed out of caste or religion. However, in some marriages taking place within a particular caste were also registered, most of such cases they were performed without the consent and sanction of respective families, or even in some cases the consent of one family was taken while the counterpart family was missing. There were numerous cases whereby most of the witnesses were none of the family members, however, either friend of any of the couples getting married.

On the one side there was a hard caste system on the other side there was a liberal urban ecosystem that either tolerated such marriages or did not bother at all. Most of such marriages faced criminal cases lodged by either or both of the families. Even if they were facing difficulties in getting premises on rent.

The worst social problem is witnessed in the rural areas where such a couple is boycotted. In some cases, their property in the rural areas was captured or abandoned, and even families of such members residing in villages were taunted and even tortured. In many cases ultimately even it became impossible for such families to live peacefully in their native villages and they were made to migrate to any safe or unknown places.

One of the major social problems occurred with the children born of such out-of-caste and out-of-religious marriages. They are usually not accepted by any of the castes belonging to their parents. Although modern constitutional and legal provisions protect the interests and rights of such couples.

Outcastes in rural and urban areas resulted in different reasons. In urban areas, outcastes were those marrying out of their castes and their children while in rural areas outcastes existed due to certain imposition of control or disciplinary action against a particular member of the family of the caste or social groups. Outcastes in rural areas could return to their original castes after some period or removal of sanctions by the larger caste societies, however, in urban areas, it's become very difficult for them to get a reentry into their original castes. In this manner, outcasting in urban areas is a permanent phenomenon.

During the survey of almost 138 out-of-caste marriages, we found no single evidence that any kind of reentry was possible into their original caste through any means. Although some talk about the caste of the father would be the basis of determining the caste of the children due to a patrilineal system in practice, however, mere writing or mentioning the father's caste as their caste reentry into the bigger caste set was never possible for and they remained outcastes as possible.

Caste dynamics have two distinct features *casting* and *casting out*. Casting has created, sustained, and promoted various castes of Bihar whereas outcasting leads to the disorganization of a caste. In addition, *casting* leads to coexistence, sharing of common territory and practices, endogamy, and solidarity. Both *casting* and *casting out* have remained present in the Indian social history or the history of caste. Castes are organized, disorganized, and reorganized. This has been a continuous phenomenon in Indian social life. Caste would be losing its static and constant entity. It is generally affected by out-of-caste marriages. However, out-of-caste marriages have affected the stability of the original castes of the two persons mutually getting married. Children born of such marriages in general are not accepted by any of the two castes. They, however, due to certain governmental provisions continue to mention the caste of either the mother or father as their caste. However, it would be always controversial to decide a caste of the caste of a child born out of any inter-caste or inter-religious marriage.

The study has revealed that three major concerns promoted casting and it was to protect the specific biology, economy, solidarity, culture, and philosophy. People who were not willing to lose their biological features promoted and patronized the caste system.

The study has found that there were some specific and mixed reasons for preferring an out-of-caste marriage. Such reasons varied from individual to individual and mainly individual situations and preferences were the main reason. It was found that younger children of a family majorly performed inter-caste or inter-religious marriages. In some cases, gender issues also played a significant role whereby any girl belonging to the upper caste got married to any backward or Dalit caste individual mainly to satisfy their femininity of having an upper hand. Many families were due to financial limitations were not able to find a suitable girl and a boy within their caste. Even due to the proximity of habitation, especially in urban settings girls and boys usually came in mutual contact and became a mutual lover leading to marriage. In some cases, due to pre-marital sexual affairs, a girl gets pregnant, leaving behind no choice but to undergo inter-caste or inter-religious marriage.

Conclusion

The study reveals that caste dynamics in Bihar are deeply ingrained in the social fabric, with casting and outcasting playing significant roles in shaping social interactions and institutions. While outcasting is a major consequence of defying traditional caste rules, particularly through inter-caste and inter-religious marriages, the research shows that this phenomenon leads to the social exclusion of individuals and families, with little possibility of reentry into their original caste. The persistence of caste-based identities, despite legal protections and urbanization, indicates that caste remains a powerful determinant of social relationships and structures in India. This research highlights the complexities of caste as both a cultural and social system and calls for a reexamination of caste dynamics in light of contemporary social changes. Further studies are needed to address the challenges posed by outcasting and to develop strategies for promoting social integration and reducing caste-based discrimination.

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